

JOINING PROCESS OF ALUMINA BORATE WHISKERS REINFORCED ALUMINUM COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: Alumina borate whisker reinforced aluminum composite which is considered as a advanced material with high properties and low cost. In this study, the joining processes was studied using alumina borate whisker reinforced aluminum-copper alloy composite in semi-solid state. The microstructure and the joint strengths of the joining interface were investigated. Both composites were connected directly with a wide aluminum band, no pore and crack can be found at the joining interface. The whiskers which exited at the jointing interface play a key role for the joining. The joint strengths is higher than matrix alloy. Moreover, the joint strength could be improved by T4 treatment. It was revolted that the composites could be successfully joined to themselves.

KEYWORDS: alumina borate whisker, aluminum matrix composite, semi-solid state, joining interface, joint strength.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites exhibit high specific strength, elastic modules and good high-temperature properties. These properties offer a wide application spectrum in aerospace industries and make them attractive materials for airframe and spacecraft structure. There are some problems which hinder the engineering application of MMCs in structure components: the high cost and the secondary procedures. Two steps are necessary for MMCs to achieve application in industry: the fabrication of MMCs and the secondary procedures, especially the joining of MMCs. Among the different secondary procedures for structure component fabrication, joining of MMCs is fundamental for the production of complex structures. Joining technologies are essential for practical application of MMCs[1]. The fabrication processes for MMCs are being overcome by many efforts, however, there has been litter study concerning joining processes of the materials. Thus, the paper aims to study these processes using alumina borate whiskers reinforced aluminum composite which is considered as a advanced material with high properties and low cost[2,3].

EXPERIMENTAL

The composite used in this study was an Al-Cu alloy reinforced by 20% volume fraction alumina borate whiskers. The chemical composition of matrix alloy is 4.5wt% Cu, 0.6wt% Mn, 0.15wt% Ti, 94.75wt% Al. The composite was fabricated by squeeze casting method. The dimension of the composite is $\phi 50 \times 25$ mm.

The to-be-jointed specimens were cut from the parent composite material, along the center line of the material. The joint form is butt joint. Its schematic diagram was shown in Fig.1.

Prior to be bonded, the specimens were treated as follows: First, the surfaces were mechanically grinded with silicon carbide papers up to 600 grade, then, they were chemically cleaned using a commercial deoxidant to reduce the alumina film thickness.

The joining experiment of the composites were carried out at the pressure of 110 MPa with the hold time of 3 min and 560 °C temperature at which the matrix is in semi-solid state.

The specimens blanks were cut from the different position of the butt joining interface of the material which had been joined for microstructure study, using scanning electron microscopy(SEM).

The tensile specimens of joining interface were studied both in the as-bonded state and in T4 heat treated state. The T4 treatment is at 540 °C for 8 hours. The direction selected for tensile specimen and the dimension of the specimen were shown in Fig.2.

The tests of bond strength were carried out using Instron-1186 type electron testing machine, at room temperature, with a speed of 0.5 mm/min.

RESULTS

From the microstructure of butt joining interface in Fig.3, it can be observed that a wide aluminum band exists at the interface, which was connected directly with both composites. The matrix band is continuous in the joint composite from top to bottom. The width of the matrix band is almost same. The unbonded part does not exist at the whole material. At the initial stage of butt joining process, the surfaces to be jointed were not connected directly and a small gap existed. In this case, the matrix and whiskers in the composite could not flow at the same time, the flow rate of matrix with the semi-solid state in the composite may be quicker than that of the motion or deformation of the surface to be jointed, so the matrix with semi-solid was squeezed from composites to break the oxide film of the to-be-jointed surface and formed the matrix band.

Fig.4 is the high magnification micrograph of butt joining interface, it can be found that litter whiskers exist at both of the interface and the aluminum band. The whiskers were broken during the joining process and moved along with the flowing matrix. The oxide film can easily be broken by these whiskers. The break oxide films and the existence of break whiskers at joining interface play an important role for joining process. In this case, the joint strength of the joining interface is higher than that of the matrix alloy. After T4 treated, the strength can be improved.

The joining interface was not break during tensile test, which revolted that the joint state is good. Moreover, no pore and crack can be found as shown in Fig.3 and Fig.4.

As discussion above, the joint process of the composite in semi-solid state can be concluded as follows: the first step is the formation of the semi-solid aluminum band. Because the to-be-jointed surface was unfair in micro-scale, the gaps should exist, during deformation of the composite, the aluminum alloy with semi-solid state can flow out from the surface, which

lead to the aluminum band formation with semi-solid state; the second step is the aluminum band solidification, which results in the joining of the two parts of the composite.

Because aluminum film at the to-be-joined surface can obstruct the joining of the composite, to break the aluminum film is very important for the joining process of the composite.

CONCLUSIONS

On the basis of the above analysis, the following conclusions were provided:

1. The alumina borate whiskers reinforced aluminum composite can be joined to themselves using butt joint in semi-solid. The joint state is good.
2. The joining strength of bonding interface is higher than that of matrix alloy, it could be improved by T4 treatment in butt joint.
3. The break of oxide films of the to-be-joined surface and the existence of whiskers in the jointed interface play a key role for the joining.

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Fig.1 Schematic diagram joint form for the composite joining

Fig. 2 Direction selected for tensile specimen and the dimension of the specimen

Fig.3 SEM micrograph of the jointed interface

Fig. 4 Higher magnification SEM micrograph of the jointed interface